

Evaluation of 3D-Printed Concrete Properties for Tunnel Structure Rehabilitation

Muhammad Mubashar Ejaz ✉

Department of Civil Engineering Technology,
Punjab Tianjin University of Technology, Pakistan

Muhammad Adeel

School of Civil Engineering and Architecture,
Wuhan University of Technology, Wuhan, China

Adeel Rehman

Department of Architectural Engineering Technology,
Punjab Tianjin University of Technology, Pakistan

Muhammad Abubakar

Department of Civil Technology,
Government College of Technology, Bahawalpur, Pakistan

Shah Zaib

Department of Civil Engineering,
Institute of Southern Punjab, Pakistan

Sheraz Hussain

Department of Automotive Engineering Technology,
Punjab Tianjin University of Technology, Pakistan

ABSTRACT:

3D printing technology has developed as a revolutionary method for the repair of tunnel structures, meeting the escalating demands of contemporary urbanization, especially in subway systems. This study analyses the mechanical and material aspects of 3D-printed concrete, concentrating on novel alterations to boost performance. Research examined the impact of biochar as an addition on the hydration, flowability, pumpability, and mechanical qualities of 3D-printed concrete across different dosages and ages. The feasibility of ultrasonic wave velocity as a non-destructive technique for evaluating ultra-early-age mechanical characteristics of 3D-printed cement-based materials was assessed. Tests for ultrasonic wave velocity and uniaxial compressive strength were conducted on cement paste, regular mortar, and mortar improved with additives for 3D printing. The findings indicate that biochar markedly affects the shrinkage, constructability, and overall mechanical performance of 3D-printed concrete, while ultrasonic wave velocity has a robust link with early-age mechanical parameters. These findings provide a scientific basis for enhancing 3D-printed materials and techniques, hence improving their use in tunnel repair and rehabilitation.

Keywords: 3D printing, tunnel structure repair, 3D-printed concrete, biochar, hydration performance, architecture, design, cement-based materials.

Suggested Citation: M.M. Ejaz, M. Adeel, A. Rehman, M. Abubakar, S. Zaib, S. Hussain, "Evaluation of 3D-Printed Concrete Properties for Tunnel Structure Rehabilitation," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(6), pp. 133-141, Nov-Dec 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(6\).12](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(6).12)

INTRODUCTION

The growing complexity of subway tunnel settings and the operational limitations imposed by restricted maintenance periods have made conventional tunnel repair techniques unable to satisfy contemporary requirements [1-2]. These constraints underscore an immediate necessity for novel strategies to improve the quality and efficiency of tunnel structure rehabilitation. In response, 3D printing technology has developed as an innovative option, providing customized, flexible, and efficient approaches for construction and repair [3]. Shoukat et al. [4] proposed a 3D model of smart home using digital twin technology. Tao et al. [5] conducted research on 3D printing construction technology for tunnel lining structures. Although 3D printing demonstrates potential in tunnel engineering, its utilization for underground tunnel repairs is still experimental.

The effectiveness of 3D printing in tunnel repairs axes on the advancement of appropriate materials with superior qualities. 3D-printed concrete must harmonize essential characteristics such as pumpability, flowability, and mechanical performance to attain optimal constructability. Researchers have examined several material modifications to fulfill these needs. Sun et al. [6] boosted the constructability of PVA-ECC using carbon nanotubes, whereas Shakor et al. [7] improved the workability of concrete through the incorporation of lithium carbonate. Long et al. [8] demonstrated enhanced interlayer bonding strength with glass fiber additions, and employed microcrystalline cellulose to improve workability. These improvements highlight the need of material optimization in realizing effective 3D printing solutions.

Soltan et al. [9] studied the relationship between various components and the flowability of concrete and found that the addition of cellulose ether, attapulgite clay, or aluminate cement would reduce the flowability of concrete and have varying degrees of impact on its hardening rate. Biochar is a carbon rich product generated by biomass pyrolysis under anaerobic or anaerobic conditions, which contains abundant pores, stable structure, and no pollution. Huang et al. [10] found that biochar can effectively achieve energy conservation, emission reduction, and water purification by partially replacing cement in concrete. Currently, there is limited research on the impact of biochar on the performance of 3D printed concrete. Notwithstanding its potential, considerable research gaps remain:

- Limited research on the application of 3D printing technology specifically for subway tunnel repairs.
- Insufficient understanding of the effects of biochar as an additive on the properties of 3D-printed concrete, including hydration, flowability, pumpability, and shrinkage behavior.
- Lack of established methods to evaluate the ultra-early-age mechanical properties of 3D-printed cement-based materials.

This work addresses these shortcomings by making the following key contributions:

- Investigated the impact of biochar on the hydration, flowability, pumpability, mechanical properties, and shrinkage behavior of 3D-printed concrete for tunnel repairs.
- Introduced biochar as a sustainable additive to enhance the performance and environmental benefits of 3D-printed concrete.
- Advanced the understanding of material behavior in 3D printing, paving the way for its practical implementation in urban transportation infrastructure repair.

PERTINENT LITERATURE

Recent breakthroughs in 3D printing technology have revolutionized building and maintenance techniques for tunnel structures, emphasizing material optimization and mechanical performance in research. Substantial advancements have occurred in the field; nonetheless, obstacles persist, especially regarding early-age material characteristics and new additions such as biochar. Table 1

compares 3D printing technology for tunnel structure repair with other standard and new repair methodologies.

Table 1. Advantages of 3D Printing over Other Technologies

Technology	Key Features	Advantages	Limitations	Comparison with 3D Printing
Traditional Concrete Repair [11]	Manual or machine-applied concrete placement, including patching, grouting, and shotcrete.	Widely available. Established methodologies. Cost-effective for small-scale repairs.	Labor-intensive. Time-consuming. Difficult to use in confined spaces like subway tunnels.	3D printing is faster and less labor-intensive. Offers better precision in confined spaces.
Shotcrete (Sprayed Concrete) [12]	Pneumatically applied concrete used for repair and stabilization.	Rapid application. Good adhesion in uneven areas. Versatile in various environments.	High rebound material loss. Limited control over material composition. High setup cost.	It reduces material waste and offers customizable compositions.
Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (FRC) [13]	Concrete with added fibers (e.g., glass, carbon) to improve mechanical properties.	Enhanced durability and tensile strength. Effective for crack control and load resistance.	Difficult to achieve uniform dispersion of fibers. Limited adaptability for complex shapes.	It allows precise control over material distribution and structural designs.
Precast Concrete Segments [14]	Prefabricated concrete elements assembled on-site for tunnel lining or repair.	High-quality control. Faster on-site assembly. Reusable molds for similar structures.	Heavy and difficult to transport. Requires large cranes and specialized equipment.	It eliminates transportation challenges and adapts to unique tunnel geometries.
Polymer-Modified Concrete [15]	Concrete modified with polymers to improve adhesion, flexibility, and durability.	High resistance to chemical attacks. Improved durability in harsh environments.	Expensive materials. Limited performance in load-bearing applications.	It allows integration of polymers into designs while enabling higher adaptability.
Self-Healing Concrete [16]	Concrete with embedded capsules or bacteria to repair cracks autonomously.	Long-term durability. Minimal maintenance required. Reduces long-term costs.	High initial costs. Limited strength and load-bearing capacity during initial curing.	It can combine self-healing materials for enhanced repair outcomes.
3D Printing Technology [17]	Layer-by-layer deposition of concrete using robotic systems and specialized nozzles for precise construction.	High precision and customization. Reduced material waste. Adaptability to confined spaces.	Expensive initial setup. Requires specialized expertise. Limited large-scale implementation.	Combines adaptability and precision unmatched by traditional technologies. Sustainable material options like biochar.

Although there is potential for the use of 3D printing in tunnels for experimental purposes, further development is necessary before it can be implemented on a broad scale.

Tunnel Rehabilitation

The utilization of 3D printing in tunnel repairs has increased owing to its versatility, accuracy, and efficacy. The Swissloop Tunnelling (SLT) team conducted groundbreaking research on 3D-printed tunnel lining structures, emphasizing the technology's potential to tackle the issues posed by tight settings and restricted maintenance periods in subway systems [18]. Likewise, research conducted by Baduge et al. [19] investigated building methodologies utilizing 3D-printed concrete; nevertheless, practical application in subway tunnels is still experimental.

Concrete 3D-Printed

The printability of 3D-printed concrete depends on balancing pumpability, flowability, and mechanical strength. Numerous researchers have altered concrete formulations to enhance these characteristics. With the purpose of enhancing the constructability of concrete, Muthukrishnan et al.

[20] gave a comprehensive assessment of the investigations that have been reported. For the purpose of enhancing the constructability of geopolymer concrete, they also offered some novel ideas and some results. Zhang et al. [21] introduced cutting-edge mix design concepts for 3D printed concrete (3DPC). They emphasized numerous aspects of mixture compositions and their effect on the features of 3DPC, while also detailing mix design methodologies. In response to the identified deficiencies, Umar et al. [22] identified nine potential criteria and thirty-two corresponding metrics that influence the choice to adopt 3D printing technology in construction projects. The findings revealed that the primary critical variables for the successful implementation of 3D printing technology in construction are “technology compatibility”, “supply-side advantages”, and “complexity”.

Additives in Concrete

The incorporation of sustainable additives like biochar has created new opportunities for improving the environmental performance of concrete. Biochar, a carbon-dense residue of biomass pyrolysis, has advantages such as energy conservation, emission reduction, and enhanced mechanical characteristics when utilized as a partial alternative for cement. Vergara et al. [23] intended to employ a circular economy strategy for the integration of biochar powder derived from wood biomass gasification (at 0, 5, 10, 15, and 20 wt%) with regular Portland cement and additive manufacturing, particularly utilizing the direct ink writing technique. This approach is applicable on a wide scale and at minimal cost. Falliano et al. [11] reported initial findings from ongoing research focused on demonstrating the potential decrease in the environmental impact of concrete through the integration of two interrelated strategies: utilizing by-products, specifically biochar, in the production of 3D printable cementitious composites. The incorporation of biochar results in the mixes exhibiting exceptional dimensional stability in the fresh condition, as assessed by the extrusion test.

This work enhances prior research by including biochar as a sustainable additive and employing ultrasonic testing methods to assess early-age mechanical qualities, with the objective of advancing 3D printing technology for tunnel structure repairs.

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

Raw Materials

This experiment uses silica sand with a maximum particle size of 2 mm, Portland cement (CEM I 52.5N) provided by Holcim, cement density of 3160 kg/m³, and Burgundy specific surface area of 4080 cm²/g. The chemical composition and loss on ignition (LOI) of cement. The water reducing agent is from BASF (Master Glenium 51), and the cellulose ether is from Shin Etsu (MOT 60000 YP4). Biochar comes from Carboganic. The scanning electron microscope of biochar is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Scanning Electron Microscopy Images of Biochar at Different Scales

Mix Proportion Design

The water cement ratio in this experiment is 0.35, and the sand cement ratio of the mixed material is 1. The amount of biochar added to the mixed materials (Cement-Biochar) CB2, CB4, and CB6 is 2%, 4%, and 6% of the cement mass, respectively. The mixed material CB0 without added biochar was used as the control group. The mix proportion design of all mixing materials is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Mix Proportion Design of Mixing Materials with Different Doses of Biochar (Unit: kg/m³)

Mixing material	Sand	Cement	Water	Water reducing agent	Cellulose ether	Biochar
CB0	958	958	335.3	3.382	0.958	0
CB2	958	958	335.3	3.382	0.958	19.2
CB4	958	958	335.3	3.382	0.958	38.3
CB6	958	958	335.3	3.382	0.958	57.5

RESULTS

Hydration Performance

According to the EN196-9 standard, the hydration performance of mixed material samples with different doses of biochar added was evaluated using a commercial Thermometric TAM Air. The hydration heat release rate and cumulative hydration heat release rate of the mixed material samples with different doses of biochar are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Hydration Heat Release Rate and Cumulative Hydration Heat Release Rate of Mixed Material Samples with Different Doses of Biochar Added

All samples exhibited typical hydration behavior of Portland cement, with two exothermic peaks present during the hydration process. From Figure 2, it can be seen that the second exothermic peak of hydration of the mixture containing biochar appears slightly earlier. In addition, the cumulative heat release of CB6 at 7 days of age (328.26 J/g of adhesive) was 1.3% higher than that of the reference group CB0, further indicating this point. This subtle difference can be attributed to the nucleation process of biochar. However, due to the inert nature of biochar, its impact on the hydration of 3D printed concrete is very limited.

Liquidity and pumpability

This experiment uses a commercial rheometer to evaluate the rheological properties of freshly mixed materials, and each group of mixtures is tested twice. The CB6 mixture is too hard to measure, so the flow curves of CB0, CB2, and CB4 mixtures are shown in Figure 3. The yield stress and plastic viscosity values can be obtained by measuring the slope of the curve and the y-axis intercept in the image. In addition, a peristaltic pump (Rudolf STROBOT 407) equipped with a rubber tube (length 5 m, diameter 25.4 mm) was used to transport fresh materials in the experiment, and the pumping pressure loss was measured through a pressure sensor at the pump outlet. Each group of mixed materials was tested twice.

Figure 3. Flow Curves of Mixed Materials with Different Amounts of Biochar Addition

DISCUSSION

This study's findings emphasize the diverse impacts of integrating biochar into 3D-printed concrete for tunnel structure rehabilitation. This talk examines the ramifications of these studies and their potential to resolve issues in material performance and practical application.

The nucleation effect of biochar, demonstrated by its capacity to marginally advance the second exothermic peak of cement hydration, indicates that biochar offers supplementary nucleation sites, hence expediting the initial hydration process. This action can enhance the early strength development of 3D-printed concrete, particularly in situations necessitating rapid setting, such as constrained tunnel repair intervals. The lack of novel hydration phases suggests that biochar does not chemically engage with the hydration products, hence guaranteeing compatibility with traditional cementitious systems.

The augmentation of dynamic yield stress and plastic viscosity with biochar incorporation indicates its capacity to enhance the stability of the concrete mixture during extrusion in 3D printing. These qualities are essential for preserving the structural integrity of printed layers and averting distortion during deposition. Nevertheless, the concomitant rise in pumping pressure presents practical difficulties, including the potential for pipeline obstructions. This constraint highlights the necessity for optimization of biochar dosage or modifications in mix composition to attain a balance between workability and printability.

The influence of biochar on early-age mechanical properties, especially the notable rise in static yield stress, indicates its potential to improve structural stability during the crucial initial phases of 3D printing. The decrease in flexural strength with increased biochar content signifies a compromise

between initial performance and enduring mechanical qualities. This trade-off may arise from the porous characteristics of biochar, which can serve as vulnerabilities inside the solidified matrix. Future research may investigate surface changes or alternative forms of biochar to alleviate this effect.

The significant decrease in self-shrinkage resulting from biochar incorporation is a favourable development for mitigating shrinkage-related cracking, a prevalent problem in tunnel rehabilitation. The capacity of biochar to absorb and retain water certainly contributes significantly to this phenomenon, functioning as an internal healing agent. Nonetheless, the minimal impact on drying shrinkage indicates that biochar alone may be unable to resolve all shrinkage-related issues. An integrated approach, incorporating biochar with shrinkage-reducing admixtures, may be investigated to improve overall efficacy.

The incorporation of biochar into 3D-printed concrete corresponds with the increasing necessity for sustainable and effective repair technologies in tunnel engineering. The capacity to increase early-age characteristics and diminish self-shrinkage renders biochar-enhanced concrete a feasible choice for swift and resilient repairs. Nonetheless, the practical obstacles related to elevated pumping pressure and diminished flexural strength must be resolved to facilitate wider use.

Biochar, a carbon-dense and eco-friendly substance, enhances the sustainability of 3D-printed concrete. Biochar can mitigate carbon emissions linked to cement manufacturing by serving as a partial substitute for cement, thereby advancing global initiatives for sustainable construction practices. Nonetheless, its application must be assessed regarding lifecycle performance and any trade-offs, including the energy necessary for its manufacturing.

The research emphasizes the combined advantages and obstacles of integrating biochar into 3D-printed concrete for tunnel rehabilitation. Although its capacity to improve hydration kinetics, rheological properties, and self-shrinkage has distinct benefits, practical issues like workability and long-term strength necessitate additional research. Biochar presents potential as a novel material for the sustainable and effective repair of tunnel structures, contingent upon meticulous optimization of its application.

CONCLUSION

This study carefully examined the effects of biochar as an addition in 3D-printed concrete for the restoration of tunnel structures. The subsequent conclusions can be derived from the experimental results: 1) Biochar, owing to its nucleation impact, somewhat accelerates the second exothermic peak in the cement hydration process. The use of biochar did not create any new hydration phases in the concrete, hence affirming its inertness in modifying the essential chemical processes. 2) The incorporation of biochar enhances the dynamic yield stress and plastic viscosity of fresh concrete. The improvement in rheological qualities enhances the mix's uniformity but also increases the pumping pressure, which may lead to issues such as pipeline clogs during application. And 3) biochar enhances the uniformity and static yield stress of early-age concrete. As the biochar concentration increased from 0% to 4%. This enhancement underscores the capacity of biochar to augment the stability and strength of newly laid concrete. The incorporation of biochar in 3D-printed concrete demonstrates potential for increasing early-age characteristics, minimizing self-shrinkage, and enhancing uniformity, rendering it appropriate for tunnel structure rehabilitation where swift mechanical strength and reduced cracking are essential. Nonetheless, issues like as elevated pumping pressure and diminished flexural strength must be resolved for wider practical implementation.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. D. Lin, Z. Zhou, M. Weng, W. Broere, and J. Cui, "Metro systems: Construction, operation and impacts," *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, vol. 143, p. 105373, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.tust.2023.105373.
2. Y. Zhao, Y. Liu, and E. Mu, "A Review of Intelligent Subway Tunnels Based on Digital Twin Technology," *Buildings*, vol. 14, no. 8, p. 2452, 2024, doi: 10.3390/buildings14082452.
3. S. Besklubova, M. J. Skibniewski, and X. Zhang, "Factors affecting 3D printing technology adaptation in construction," *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, vol. 147, no. 5, p. 04021026, 2021, doi: 10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0002034.
4. M. U. Shoukat *et al.*, "Smart home for enhanced healthcare: exploring human machine interface oriented digital twin model," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 83, no. 11, pp. 31297–31315, 2024, doi: 10.1007/s11042-023-16875-9.
5. Y. Tao, K. Lesage, K. Van Tittelboom, Y. Yuan, and G. De Schutter, "Influence of substrate surface roughness and moisture content on tensile adhesion performance of 3D printable concrete," *Cement and Concrete Composites*, vol. 126, p. 104350, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2021.104350.
6. X. Sun, Q. Wang, H. Wang, and L. Chen, "Influence of multi-walled nanotubes on the fresh and hardened properties of a 3D printing PVA mortar ink," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 247, p. 118590, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.118590.
7. P. Shakor, J. Sanjayan, A. Nazari, and S. Nejadi, "Modified 3D printed powder to cement-based material and mechanical properties of cement scaffold used in 3D printing," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 138, pp. 398–409, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2017.02.037.
8. W. J. Long *et al.*, "Rheology and buildability of sustainable cement-based composites containing micro-crystalline cellulose for 3D-printing," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 239, p. 118054, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118054.
9. D. G. Soltan and V. C. Li, "A self-reinforced cementitious composite for building-scale 3D printing," *Cement and Concrete Composites*, vol. 90, pp. 1–13, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2018.03.017.
10. Y. Huang *et al.*, "Application of pervious concrete pavement in the 'breathe in-breathe out' design for sponge cities in China," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, pp. 1–20, 2024, doi: 10.1007/s11356-024-33760-6.
11. L. Czarnecki, R. Geryło, and K. Kuczyński, "Concrete repair durability," *Materials*, vol. 13, no. 20, p. 4535, 2020, doi: 10.3390/ma13204535.
12. F. Heidarneshad and Q. Zhang, "Shotcrete based 3D concrete printing: State of art, challenges, and opportunities," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 323, p. 126545, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2022.126545.
13. C. Zhao *et al.*, "Research on different types of fiber reinforced concrete in recent years: An overview," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 365, p. 130075, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2022.130075.
14. F. Di Carlo, A. Meda, and Z. Rinaldi, "Design procedure for precast fibre-reinforced concrete segments in tunnel lining construction," *Structural Concrete*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 747–759, 2016, doi: 10.1002/suco.201500194.
15. J. B. Kardon, "Polymer-modified concrete," *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 85–92, 1997, doi: 10.1061/(ASCE)0899-1561(1997)9:2(85).
16. K. Vijay, M. Murmu, and S. V. Deo, "Bacteria based self healing concrete—A review," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 152, pp. 1008–1014, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2017.07.040.

17. N. Shahrubudin, T. C. Lee, and R. J. P. M. Ramlan, "An overview on 3D printing technology: Technological, materials, and applications," *Procedia Manufacturing*, vol. 35, pp. 1286–1296, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.promfg.2019.06.089.
18. Y. Tao and Y. Yuan, "3D concrete printing for tunnel linings: Opportunities and challenges," in *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 2024, vol. 1333, no. 1, p. 012039, doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/1333/1/012039.
19. S. K. Baduge *et al.*, "Improving performance of additive manufactured (3D printed) concrete: A review on material mix design, processing, interlayer bonding, and reinforcing methods," *Structures*, vol. 29, pp. 1597–1609, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.istruc.2020.12.061.
20. S. Muthukrishnan, S. Ramakrishnan, and J. Sanjayan, "Technologies for improving buildability in 3D concrete printing," *Cement and Concrete Composites*, vol. 122, p. 104144, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2021.104144.
21. C. Zhang *et al.*, "Mix design concepts for 3D printable concrete: A review," *Cement and Concrete Composites*, vol. 122, p. 104155, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2021.104155.
22. T. Umar, "Key factors influencing the implementation of three-dimensional printing in construction," *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers-Management, Procurement and Law*, vol. 174, no. 3, pp. 104–117, 2020, doi: 10.1680/jmapl.19.00029.
23. L. A. Vergara, J. F. Perez, and H. A. Colorado, "3D printing of ordinary Portland cement with waste wood derived biochar obtained from gasification," *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, vol. 18, p. e02117, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.cscm.2023.e02117.
24. D. Falliano, L. Restuccia, and G. A. Ferro, "Biochar addition for 3DCP: a preliminary study," *Procedia Structural Integrity*, vol. 41, pp. 699–703, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.prostr.2022.05.079.